

COcyber Cybersphere Insights – May 2025

From validating cooperation models for cybersecurity and civil-defence spheres to showcasing dual-use innovation on the European stage, [COcyber](#) is entering a phase of concrete outputs. This edition presents our upcoming consultation on best practices in civil-defence cybersecurity, results from the AI Cybersecurity Deephack, and our participation at @GITEX Europe 2025. It also includes selected cybersecurity news relevant to the wider digital ecosystem.

Online consultation event – Best Practice validation: Cybersecurity and Civil-Defence cooperation in the EU

 13 June 2025 | 10:00–12:00 CEST | Online

Organised by the @Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), the leading academic partner within the [COcyber](#) project, the event will bring together COcyber Ambassadors, Advisory Board members, and cybersecurity experts to assess and prioritise a shortlist of 20 best practices aimed at strengthening civil-defence cooperation across the EU.

The poster features a green background with faint binary code. At the top left is the COcyber logo. The main title is 'Online consultation event' followed by 'Best practice validation for cybersecurity and civil - defence cooperation in the EU'. A blue rounded rectangle contains the text 'Join us & contribute to strengthen European cybersecurity'. Below this, a location pin icon is next to the text 'June 13th | 10 - 12:00 CEST Online'. A QR code is positioned to the right of the date. At the bottom left is the 'Funded by the European Union' logo, and at the bottom right is the 'ECCC' logo (European Cybersecurity Competence Centre).

The interactive session will be guided by Professor @Georges Ataya and will include a concise overview of the practices, live scoring using digital tools, and a discussion to validate the final selection.

The goal: identify 10 best practices with the potential for replication across national contexts, aligned with EU strategic priorities.

Why should you join: Participants will also have the opportunity to propose their own best practices for inclusion on the COcyber platform, suggest new experts for [COcyber Ambassadors](#) Batch #3, access upcoming capacity-building activities, and join future networking and pitching events.

[Register here](#)

COcyber at GITEX EUROPE (with the winners of our AI Cybersecurity Deephack)

📍 21–23 May 2025 | Messe Berlin (Hall 4.2, Booth H4.2-E50)

COcyber will be on site at GITEX Europe 2025, hosted at our coordinator @EIT Digital's booth, to spotlight how civil-defence cybersecurity collaboration is evolving across Europe.

👏 Joining us: a representative from **Team ALVAR**, winners of the COcyber Deephack, whose AI tool secures autonomous systems by combining behavioural and signal analysis for real-time threat detection.

Eager to connect with innovators, policymakers, and tech leaders advancing Europe's cybersecurity

resilience.

[Read More](#)

Insights from COcyber AI Cybersecurity Deephack 2025: innovation, inclusion, and intensity in a dual-use cyber arena

From April 24–26, 2025, the virtual stage was set for one of the most pressing challenges in cybersecurity today: can artificial intelligence help stop the next big phishing attack? The [AI Cybersecurity Deephack: Advancing European Defence Capabilities](#) brought together a diverse mix of participants - students, PhD candidates, startup founders, and skilled cyber professionals - for a 48-hour sprint to answer exactly that.

Winning Teams

- 🥇 **Team ALVAR** (Finland) – Multimodal AI for real-time anomaly detection in autonomous systems
- 🥈 **Team Morpheous** (Belgium & Italy) – Federated learning engine balancing privacy and resilience
- 🥉 **Team Genshield AI** (Ireland) – Graph-based detection with built-in user training modules

With mentorship from industry leaders, a dynamic support programme, and post-event visibility, the Deephack was a technical sprint and a demonstration of how interdisciplinary and cross-cultural teams can build resilient, ethical AI systems under pressure.

[Learn more](#)

News from the Field

New step for EU cybersecurity: European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) develops the [European Vulnerability Database \(EUVD\)](#)

ENISA launches a public platform aggregating vulnerability data from Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRTs), vendors, and databases across Europe.

EUVD supports:

- ✓ Improved situational awareness
- ✓ Coordinated vulnerability disclosure
- ✓ Clearer mitigation guidance for digital products

www.enisa.europa.eu/news/consult-the-european-vulnerability-database-to-enhance-your-digital-security

EU Budget Boost for Defence: Commission Mobilises €910M and Proposes New Regulation

In April 2025, the European Commission proposed changes to several EU programmes, including Horizon Europe, the Digital Europe Programme, and the European Regional Development Fund, to expand support for defence-related technologies, including #dual-use applications such as #AI and cybersecurity.

Later that month, €910 million were awarded under the European Defence Fund (EDF) to 62 projects focusing on drone defence, AI-enabled aerial systems, force mobility, and disruptive technologies.

■ [Cyber Resilience Compass: Journeys Towards Resilience](#)

The @World Economic Forum and @GCSCC (Oxford) released a **practical guide for building long-term cyber resilience**. Based on 100+ expert insights, the white paper outlines seven focus areas: leadership, governance, people, process, tech, crisis response, and ecosystems.

The document provides a clear structure to help organisations identify gaps, prioritise actions, and plan for improving their resilience over time.

www.weforum.org/publications/the-cyber-resilience-compass-journeys-towards-resilience/

What's next

In the coming weeks, COcyber will finalise the **validation of best practices for civil-defence cybersecurity cooperation** through the outcomes of the June consultation. Preparations are also underway for the **next phase of our capacity-building activities**, aimed at supporting knowledge exchange and strategic collaboration across sectors. In parallel, a **new cohort of COcyber Ambassadors is taking shape**, with more updates, community actions, and events to be announced soon.

⚡ **Don't miss any future COcyber events connecting the dots between civilian and defence cyber security initiatives, join our community now at <https://cocyber.eu/user/register>**

Disclaimer

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